

Boris Čuljak, Nina Pajević, Vladan Filipović, Dimitrije Stefanović, Željana Grbović, Nemanja Đuric, Marko Panić
BioSense Institute, Novi Sad, Serbia

Introduction

- Autonomous management of blueberry orchards using an UGV platform
- Bush detection using deep learning for navigation and positioning
- Variability of plants and environmental conditions is challenging to learn
- Augmentation expands the diversity of existing data, enhancing robustness to real-world conditions
- Knowledge applicable in many tasks
- Comparison of augmentation techniques to find the most effective pipeline**

Robot and OAK-D device

Blueberry orchard

Examples of annotated images

Statistics of annotation shapes for bushes (left) and poles (right)

Dataset

- Scenes of blueberry orchard rows
- Various phenological phases
- Variety of occlusions, positions and illumination conditions
- UGV mounted RGB camera
- 7250 images 1920x1080
- Split train:val:test = 75:10:15
- Two object classes, 24830 bushes and 2986 poles

Model

- Yolo v8 nano, light and efficient
- Composite loss: classification, objectness and location loss
- Pre-trained on COCO dataset
- Input resized to 640x640

Augmentations

Color: Hue, Saturation, Value and their combination

Geometry: Translation, Flip, Zoom and their combination

Gaussian noise with different sigmas and frequencies

Cutout with different areas and aspect ratios

Collage: addition of objects copied from other images

Mix-up: weighted sum of two images

Mosaic of 4 different images

DCGAN generated bushes

Experiment

- Baseline – no augmentation
- Dataset expanded by 30% with augmented images
- Individual augmentations evaluated and compared
- Four best augmentations selected: geometry, mosaic, collage and mix-up
- Combination approaches:
 - Uniform: 7.5% of each
 - Combo: all 4 concurrently
- Approach on the full dataset:
 - 30% added using collage
 - Remaining 3 applied to the whole expanded set

Results

- Best performance improvement with mosaic and mix-up
- Geometry provides an increase
- Collage improved pole detection
 - Correcting class imbalance
- Color and noise not so effective
- DCGAN lacks realism
- Combo better than uniform
- Full-combo best overall
 - Best fit for set challenges

Detection improvement with augmentation

Experimental results for individual and combined augmentation approaches

Method	All					Bush					Pole				
	P	R	F1	mAP ₅₀	mAP ₅₀₋₉₅	P	R	F1	mAP ₅₀	mAP ₅₀₋₉₅	P	R	F1	mAP ₅₀	mAP ₅₀₋₉₅
None	0.750	0.650	0.720	0.480	0.696	0.800	0.680	0.740	0.500	0.735	0.700	0.620	0.680	0.460	0.658
Color	0.790	0.690	0.750	0.510	0.737	0.830	0.710	0.780	0.530	0.765	0.750	0.670	0.710	0.490	0.708
Geometric	0.810	0.710	0.780	0.550	0.757	0.840	0.730	0.800	0.570	0.781	0.780	0.690	0.740	0.530	0.732
Mosaic	0.800	0.720	0.760	0.530	0.758	0.820	0.740	0.790	0.550	0.778	0.780	0.700	0.740	0.520	0.738
Gaussian	0.770	0.670	0.730	0.490	0.717	0.790	0.690	0.750	0.510	0.737	0.780	0.700	0.740	0.520	0.738
Cutout	0.760	0.660	0.710	0.470	0.706	0.780	0.680	0.730	0.490	0.727	0.740	0.640	0.690	0.460	0.686
Collage	0.729	0.671	0.728	0.471	0.699	0.777	0.680	0.761	0.461	0.725	0.826	0.689	0.795	0.451	0.751
Mix-up	0.832	0.601	0.742	0.473	0.698	0.910	0.634	0.805	0.478	0.747	0.753	0.567	0.679	0.468	0.647
DCGAN	0.755	0.642	0.706	0.420	0.694	0.854	0.668	0.803	0.463	0.750	0.655	0.616	0.609	0.378	0.635
Uniform	0.829	0.656	0.732	0.766	0.461	0.831	0.700	0.760	0.815	0.461	0.827	0.612	0.703	0.716	0.461
Combo	0.775	0.712	0.742	0.792	0.475	0.844	0.755	0.797	0.849	0.470	0.706	0.670	0.688	0.735	0.480
Full-combo	0.853	0.803	0.884	0.615	0.827	0.893	0.767	0.877	0.581	0.825	0.813	0.839	0.890	0.648	0.826